

**TRANSLATING A BOOK FROM UZBEK INTO ENGLISH: URGENCY,
CHALLENGES AND THE ISSUES OF A COLLABORATION (BASED ON THE
EXAMPLE OF THE FABLE "DUNYONING ISHLARI" BY UTKIR HOSHIMOV)**

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Abstract. This article discusses the urgency of translation of Uzbek literature into English language while highlighting the possible challenges faced by translators in doing so. The article further dives into the issues of collaboration between native Uzbek translators and native English translators in doing the translation of Uzbek literature.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, literary style, native speaker, translation, collaboration, urgency, target audience, promotion, publication, challenge, case study, readers, reviewers.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается актуальность перевода узбекской литературы на английский язык, а также освещаются возможные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются переводчики при этом. В статье подробно рассматриваются вопросы сотрудничества переводчиков-носителей узбекского языка и переводчиков-носителей английского языка при переводе узбекской литературы.

Ключевые слова: узбекская литература, литературный стиль, носитель языка, перевод, сотрудничество, актуальность, целевая аудитория, продвижение, публикация, задача, тематическое исследование, читатели, рецензенты.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek adabiyotini ingliz tiliga tarjima qilishning dolzarbligi muhokama qilinib, bunda tarjimonlar duch kelishi mumkin bo'lgan qiyinchiliklarga e'tibor qanaratilgan. Maqolada o'zbek adabiyoti tarjimasini amalga oshirishda o'zbek tarjimonlari va ona ingliz tili tarjimonlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlik masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbek adabiyoti, adabiy uslub, ona tili, tarjima, hamkorlik, dolzarblik, kitobxon, targ'ibot, nashr, qiyinchilik, amaliy tadqiqotlar, o'quvchilar, muharrirlar.

The profound spiritual dimension of individuals has perpetually engendered an insatiable demand for literary works since the advent of written language. Consequently, an extensive corpus of books spanning numerous languages, both extant and archaic, has emerged. One cannot help but marvel at the remarkable creativity exhibited by authors who have adeptly captured the intricacies of past, present, and hypothetical events through the written word. Moreover, literature serves as a conduit for illuminating the authentic realities of specific temporal and geographic contexts from the author's vantage point, rendering it a paramount facet of the literary landscape. These written accounts enable subsequent generations to gain insights into the occurrences that transpired during a given era in the lives of ordinary individuals. Literature, in its depiction of historical events, delves into the underlying causative factors, thus providing a comprehensive portrayal. Additionally, the cultural tapestry of nations is prominently interwoven within the fabric of fictional works, as they often allude to the customs and traditions of the protagonists' respective origins. Consequently, it is imperative to acknowledge that the role of literature cannot be disregarded in any epoch or circumstance. The evidence substantiating this claim is encapsulated in the timeless words of Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, who astutely proclaimed, "The decline in literature indicates a decline in the nation. The two keep pace in their downward tendency."

Undoubtedly, the cultural ethos and societal customs of a nation find vivid expression in its literary creations, as authors are often profoundly influenced by the prevailing social values and the unresolved challenges experienced by their communities during the period of their literary composition. Consequently, readers are captivated by the narrative arcs of these works, which frequently draw inspiration from the events and circumstances that unfolded in the immediate surroundings of the authors. This phenomenon is exemplified in the enduring legacies of distinguished writers such as William Shakespeare, Leo Tolstoy, and Jonathan Swift, whose works bear the indelible imprints of their respective nations. For instance, a perusal of Shakespeare's renowned tragedy "Hamlet" reveals its roots in the ancient Norse legend, thereby exerting a profound influence on the formation of English cultural heritage. Similarly, Tolstoy's magnum opus "War and Peace," set against the backdrop of the Napoleonic Wars, provides readers with glimpses into the historical tapestry of the Russian Empire and its fateful encounter with the French invasion. In the case of Jonathan Swift, his seminal work "Gulliver's Travels" serves as a narrative vessel that intricately weaves together historical events of the time and the author's lived environment. By delving into these literary masterpieces, readers embark on a journey that not only entertains but also enlightens, as they gain profound insights into the intricacies of the past and the societal fabric that shaped the authors' perspectives. These works stand as enduring testaments to the integral role of literature in shedding light on the historical, cultural, and social milieu of nations throughout the ages.

The aforementioned works of fiction, including the illustrious pieces mentioned, have garnered widespread recognition across the globe for various compelling reasons, foremost among them being their availability in numerous languages. The remarkable reach of William Shakespeare's "Hamlet" serves as a striking example, as this seminal work is believed to have been translated into an astonishing 75 languages worldwide. This expansive linguistic diffusion is particularly noteworthy given the considerable diversity of languages that possess a written form. Indeed, Leo Tolstoy's monumental work, "War and Peace," has achieved widespread recognition and has been translated into numerous languages, including but not limited to French, English, and German. The extensive reach of these translations attests to the enduring global significance of Tolstoy's magnum opus. The availability of "War and Peace" in multiple languages has contributed to its enduring popularity and readership across diverse linguistic and cultural communities. These translations allow readers worldwide to engage with the profound narrative, explore its intricate themes, and appreciate the depth of Tolstoy's storytelling prowess. As evidenced by the wealth of translations, "War and Peace" transcends national boundaries and resonates with readers from various backgrounds. Its exploration of human nature, historical events, and the intricate tapestry of Russian society during the period of the Napoleonic Wars holds universal appeal, making it a literary masterpiece that captivates audiences across different linguistic spheres. The extensive translation efforts dedicated to "War and Peace" reflect the recognition of its enduring literary value and its ability to transcend cultural and linguistic barriers. This global accessibility not only broadens the readership of the work but also fosters a vibrant exchange of ideas, interpretations, and cultural perspectives among readers worldwide. The enduring literary work "Gulliver's Travels" by Jonathan Swift has garnered significant acclaim and has been widely translated into multiple languages, including French, Russian, and numerous others. The global demand for translations of this literary masterpiece underscores its universal appeal and enduring relevance. The availability of "Gulliver's Travels" in various languages has facilitated its reach and popularity among readers from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. These translations enable a

diverse range of audiences to immerse themselves in Swift's imaginative and satirical world, and to appreciate the social commentary and thought-provoking themes that permeate the narrative. The translation of "Gulliver's Travels" into languages such as French and Russian reflects its status as a widely recognized and cherished work of literature. This international reception testifies to the enduring impact of Swift's biting social critique and his skillful blending of adventure and satire. The availability of translations broadens the readership and fosters a global appreciation for the wit, creativity, and thought-provoking nature of "Gulliver's Travels." By transcending linguistic boundaries, this literary classic continues to captivate readers across cultures, inviting them to reflect on the human condition and to contemplate the underlying societal issues that Swift so astutely portrays.

The translation activities for works of Uzbek literature have been relatively limited, warranting attention and further exploration. Observing the available translations, it becomes evident that a significant majority are rendered into Russian. In many instances, these translations were undertaken by the authors themselves, given their residence in the USSR, or by others driven by various factors, including the prevailing censorship imposed on non-Russian writers during the Soviet era. However, despite these efforts, the overall reach of these translations remained somewhat constrained. One contributing factor to this limitation is the comparative scarcity of Russian-speaking nations when compared to languages such as French, Spanish, Chinese, or English. Consequently, the significance of translating Uzbek literary works into English, with its vast number of global speakers, becomes apparent. By making these works accessible in English, billions of individuals worldwide would have the opportunity to engage with the novels written in Uzbek. Simultaneously, individuals of Uzbek heritage residing abroad could proudly showcase and introduce their culture through translated Uzbek literary works, fostering an appreciation for Uzbek cultural heritage. It is crucial to emphasize the importance of translating Uzbek works of literature into English, as the absence of such translations perpetuates an unexplored realm within Uzbek literature. This is particularly relevant for individuals of Uzbek descent living in foreign countries, including the United States and various regions worldwide, who may lack direct access to the Uzbek language. Without translated works, they may encounter barriers in exploring their cultural background and heritage. While it is true that some works of Uzbek literature have been translated into English and other languages, the visibility and recognition of these translations have not been sufficiently widespread. Moreover, some translations have failed to capture the true essence of the culture and values embedded within the original texts, a matter that will be further discussed in the subsequent paragraph.

Translating a fiction book from Uzbek into English presents several challenges. These challenges include language differences, cultural context, literary style, untranslatable words and concepts, multicultural references, length and structure, and deadlines and time constraints. Firstly, Uzbek and English belong to different language families, with distinct grammatical structures, vocabularies, and idiomatic expressions. Translators must navigate these disparities to ensure that the translated text reads naturally and conveys the essence of the original work effectively. Secondly, fiction often serves as a reflection of a particular culture, incorporating its nuances, traditions, and societal norms. Translators face the challenge of understanding the cultural context embedded in the original text and conveying it authentically to an English-speaking audience. This involves addressing cultural references, idioms, proverbs, and other culturally specific elements that may not have direct equivalents in English. Thirdly, translating fiction entails preserving the author's unique writing style, literary techniques, and narrative voice. Translators must delve into

the intricacies of the original text, capturing its artistic qualities and finding appropriate equivalents or strategies to recreate the author's stylistic choices in English. This ensures that the translated work resonates with readers and maintains the intended impact of the original. Moreover, language and culture often give rise to words, expressions, or concepts that lack direct equivalents in another language. Translators must grapple with these untranslatable elements, making choices based on the context and overall meaning to effectively convey the intended ideas. They may employ strategies such as using footnotes, explanatory phrases, or cultural equivalents to bridge the linguistic gap and convey the original text's depth accurately. Additionally, fiction frequently incorporates references to specific aspects of the source culture, such as historical events, traditions, or social norms. Translators face the challenge of ensuring that these multicultural references are comprehensible and relatable to the target readership, while simultaneously avoiding potential confusion or misinterpretation. This requires cultural sensitivity and a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures. Furthermore, languages vary in terms of sentence structure, word order, and text length. Translators must carefully manage these structural disparities to ensure that the translated text flows naturally and maintains the intended pacing and structure of the original work. They must strike a balance between fidelity to the source text and readability in the target language. Lastly, translating a book is a substantial undertaking that demands considerable time and effort. Translators often face the pressure of meeting tight deadlines while maintaining translation quality. Managing time effectively becomes crucial to ensuring accuracy and linguistic finesse within the given timeline. To address these challenges, translators collaborate closely with the author, editors, and other language experts. They engage in extensive research to understand the cultural and linguistic nuances embedded in the text. Additionally, they may consult bilingual individuals who possess a deep understanding of both languages and cultures involved, ensuring that the translation remains faithful, nuanced, and compelling.

One such challenge mentioned earlier was encountered during the translation process of Utkir Hoshimov's work, titled "Dunyoning Ishlari," undertaken by translators Abdullajon Ruziev and Mark Reese into English. In the following extract the original has unique characteristics: *Keyin meni shosha-pisha ko'rpachaga o'radi. Bir mahal onamning qo'lida ketayotqanim esim da bor. Gupillatib qor yog'ayotganini his etib turardim-u, biroq yuzimga qor tushmas edi. Onamning issiq nafasi urilib turar, u sirg'anibsirg'anib borar, og'ir hansirar edi.* The translation on the other hand reads as follows: *She quickly wrapped me in a **korpacha**. I remember my mother carrying me in her arms as we passed through the blizzard swirling around us, yet none of the flakes seemed to touch my face. I felt my mother's warm breath on me as she struggled to walk through the snow, slipping and breathing heavily. We appeared to enter into a small home illuminated by a single light. My eyes grew dark again. My mother wept.* In this instance, there is a footnote on the book and in the footnote a description is given to the word *korpacha* as follows: *Korpacha is a small quilt traditionally made by Uzbek woman by hand. It is made with two layers of fabric, usually velvet-like fabric, filled with industrial cotton inside. It usually measures at least 80x120 cms and is sewn on both sides in multiple lines with 10 cms of interval.* Indeed, a correct definition has been provided for the object within the context and the employment of footnote in this instance is surely a right decision as the word *matrass* cannot fully cover the intended meaning here. Although this is one instance from the translation of the book, quite a lot of such examples can be observed in the mentioned translation. In all the instances, both translators did a professional job by providing definitions to the lexical gaps that are present between English and Uzbek languages.

The translation process is an intricate undertaking, and collaborating with multiple translators can offer several advantages for all parties involved. One notable benefit is the division of labor and the potential for enhanced accuracy and quality in the final translation. In the case of translating a novel from Uzbek into English, the collaboration between an Uzbek native speaker and a native English speaker, as exemplified in the translation of "Dunyoning Ishlari" by Abdullajon Ruziev and Mark Reese, can yield significant benefits. One crucial aspect to consider is that professional translation ideally takes place into one's mother tongue rather than from it. Therefore, a translation of a novel from Uzbek into English is most effectively executed by a native English speaker. The rationale behind this lies in the hierarchy of language acquisition, where writing is typically acquired later in the language learning process. Consequently, it becomes exceedingly challenging for a non-native English speaker to attain a native-level proficiency in written style. As a result, a translation produced by a non-native English speaker may not possess the same level of credibility and accuracy as one executed by a native English speaker. Conversely, for a non-native speaker of Uzbek, it requires a considerable amount of time and effort to fully comprehend Uzbek literary works, encompassing all the intricate details. In this regard, a collaborative effort between an Uzbek native speaker and a native English speaker proves to be an optimal solution. By combining their respective linguistic abilities and cultural insights, the translators can leverage their strengths to produce a translation that captures the essence of the original work while ensuring linguistic precision and cultural authenticity. In the specific case of the translation of "Dunyoning Ishlari," the collaboration between Abdullajon Ruziev and Mark Reese exemplified the advantages of such a partnership. Ruziev's native Uzbek proficiency and deep understanding of the source culture, combined with Reese's native English fluency and expertise in rendering written style, contributed to a translation that effectively conveyed the nuances and richness of the original work to an English-speaking audience.

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